

COMPOSING A SCHOOL SONG WITH STUDENT PARTICIPATION USING AI-BASED COMPOSITION TOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes an attempt to use an AI-based composition support system to enable students to participate in the composition of a school song for a new school that they will attend. We developed a composition support system that recommends several melodies to replace a certain bar of melody. The experimental results showed that on average the students replaced 38.5% of the melodies in one hour when using the system.

1. INTRODUCTION

In Kuwana City, Mie Prefecture, Japan, four elementary schools and one junior high school will be merged into a new integrated elementary and junior high school, Tado Gakuen. Thus, all students from the five schools that will be closed, with the exception of third graders from the current junior high school, will attend Tado Gakuen. Most schools in Japan have a school song, and this paper describes an attempt to use artificial intelligence (AI) to produce a school song for Tado Gakuen.

It is difficult for elementary and junior high school students, who are mostly musical novices, to generate new melodies and present them to the system. Therefore, we generate school song melodies in two stages: melody exploration and structure generation. The former is the process of selecting a preferred melody segment from those presented by the AI. The latter is the process of generating the musical structure.

Simply concatenating melody segments does not constitute a piece because there is no musical structure. For example, when melody A is followed by melody B , melody AB may be followed by melody A' with a slight variation of A , and melody ABA' may be followed by melody B' with a slight variation of B . The melody $ABA'B'$ is a repeating structure. We have studied the Generative Theory of Tonal Music (GTTM), in which a hierarchical musical structure is acquired through analysis, for 20 years [1–7].

The subject of this paper is the melody exploration, i.e., whether a musical novice can select his or her preferred melody from those presented by the AI. Therefore, we developed a system that allows the user to select his/her preferred melody from those presented by the AI. Approxi-

mately 160 students had a one-hour AI composition experience class using our system, and on average, they selected and replaced at least 38.5% of the entire piece.

2. MELODY EXPLORATION INTERFACE

As shown in Fig. 1, we developed a user interface in which the user selects a bar to be changed and presses the button marked “AI” on the upper right of the screen, and the AI presents six melodies that can be replaced with the bar. The user selects his or her preferred melody from the six presented, and the piece gradually becomes his or her preference.

2.1 Interface Design

Since the system uses music notation with staves in elementary and junior high school classes, we decided to display the music notation on the interface screen. In addition, since few children are able to read the music notation completely, we made it possible to play back the replaceable melodies for confirmation.

Figure 1. Melody exploration interface.

The lyrics were written by Kuwana City residents including former principals of the elementary and junior high schools that will be merged, so the melody needs to be created to fit the lyrics. Considering that the song will be sung by elementary and junior high school students, the following restrictions were placed on the melodies initially presented and recommended.

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- Use note values that are multiples of eighths, since short notes and complex rhythms are difficult to vocalize.
- Pitch should be in the range of A3 to E5 to match the typical vocal range of elementary and junior high school students.
- The number of notes should range from +2 or -1¹ to the number of lyric moras² in a bar.
- The beat should be 4/4 or 3/4.

2.2 Template Design

Composing a melody on the basis of only AI-based recommendations is likely to result in an inconsistent and broken melody. We therefore created a template for the pieces, called Basic Music-XML, so that the pieces would not break up too much. One of them is selected when the user interface is started up. The majority of the bars in Basic-MusicXML are then replaced with those recommended by the AI, and the initial melody is displayed. Bars not replaced with the initial melody to the recommended melody were determined by a professional composer. Repeating the recommendation does not change the chord progression³.

2.3 Implementation

The system is designed to run web and server applications in a client-server model (Fig. 2). The central processing unit (CPU) of the server machine is an Intel Core i9 10940X running 14 cores and 28 threads [8]. The server machine’s graphics processing unit (GPU) is an Nvidia Geforce RTX3090 [9].

Fig. 1 shows the melody exploration user interface web app that we developed. When the user clicks on a bar that they want to change, the bar is selected, and the notes turn blue. Clicking on the AI icon in the upper-right corner of

¹ The numbers indicate increases or decreases in the number of notes.

² The number of moras is the number of rhythms of words. The languages of the world are divided into syllabic and mora languages, with Japanese being a mora language.

³ The chord progression of the template is maintained.

the screen displays the six melodies sent from the server to replace the bar. On the left side of the web app, there is a save/restore button that allows users to save a score they are working on or reopen a previously saved score.

Nginx [10] and uWSGI [11] were used as the web server application. We prepared 14 threads of uWSGI, the same number of CPU cores. uWSGI can have 512 connections per thread, so it can serve 7168 (=14×512) requests in total.

OSMD Audio Player was used to play the melody of the piece [12], and the candidate melodies were played utilizing html-midi-player [13]. The sound source was created on the server and then transferred to the client to enable playback.

The staves of the pieces were displayed using Open Sheet Music Display [14]. For displaying candidate melodies, thumbnail images were created on the server side using Open Sheet Music Display and then transferred to the client.

2.4 Melody Recommendation AI

The melody exploration user interface is implemented to present melodies that can replace user-selected bars by structure-based music generation methods such as the melody morphing method [15, 16], melody rendering method [17], and melody reduction [1] based on GTTM. However, the above methods have not yet been implemented in real time, so we decided to use a different method for this implementation.

Various AI-based melody generators have been proposed [18–20]. We implement our system in such a way that various publicly available melody generators can be used. In this study, we use Magenta’s Improv_RNN, which can estimate melodies on the basis of chord progressions [18]. Improv_RNN has three different settings— BasicImprov, AttentionImprov, and ChordPitchImprov—but the first two can only be used with triad chords, so we used the ChordPitchImprov setting here, which can be used with chords of four or more notes. The trained model we utilized was chord_pitches_improv.mag.

Figure 2. Implementation in client-server model.

2.5 Melody Generation

To call Magenta’s Improv_RNN from the melody exploration interface, we implemented Magenta to run as a server application. Since loading the network for estimation takes a lot of time, the estimation process was designed to load the network in advance, estimate a melody, and then wait for the next estimation without terminating. The results of measurements of estimation speed showed that the average estimation time for Magenta’s Improv_RNN was 360 ms. Since the server processes estimations sequentially, if for example ten estimation requests are submitted at the same time, they take 3.6 seconds to process.

If there are too many requests, the estimation may not be completed in time, so the server stops the estimation process three seconds or more after a request is submitted and presents a melody selected at random from a melody pool created in advance.

2.6 Initial Melody Candidate and Melody Pool

If significant number of students start the melody exploration user interface at the same time at the beginning of a class and Improv_RNN is called often to replace most of the bars in Basic-MusicXML, the load on the GPU will increase. If the system repeatedly times out and cannot generate the initial melody, the user interface cannot be used. Therefore, we estimated 100 initial melodies for each of the four Basic-MusicXMLs, creating a total of 400 candidate initial melodies. When the user interface is launched, the initial melody is randomly selected from the 100 candidate melodies.

The melody pool contains 100 estimated melodies for each bar for each of the four Basic-MusicXMLs. Thumbnail images of melodies in the melody pool are created in advance and stored on the server.

3. RESULTS

We held four one-hour composition experience classes with approximately 40 participants per class, for a total of approximately 160 participants. The first three classes were attended by sixth-grade elementary students planning to attend the new integrated elementary and junior high school, and the fourth class was attended by students in the junior high school brass band and local officials, including the junior high school’s former principal. There were ten computers in the classroom where the experience took place, and each group of approximately four students used one computer. To save time for switching between people operating the computers and to give each person more time to operate the computers, a mirrored screen was shown on an additional display, and an additional keyboard and mouse were provided.

3.1 Replacement Rate

Since the class time was limited to one hour, there was insufficient time to replace every bar of a piece. Therefore, we surveyed how many bars students replaced. Some

Figure 3. AI Composition Experience Class.

bars of the initial piece were the same as the melody in Basic-MusicXML. If the melody of those bars differed from the melody in Basic-MusicXML after the class, then the melody was considered to have been replaced. The percentages of melodies replaced differed among the four Basic-MusicXML bars and are shown in Table 1. Basic-MusicXML A and B, which have shorter bars, resulted in fewer replaced melodies than Basic-MusicXML C and D, which have more bars.

	A	B	C	D	Ave.
Replacement rate (%)	23.3	33.3	48.0	53.0	38.5

Table 1. Average replacement rate.

Pieces by Basic-MusicXML A and B comprised 22 bars in 4/4. The melody of the initial piece was the same as in Basic-MusicXML with six bars in A and B. The six bars were the same bar numbers in A and B, i.e., 1, 4, 8, 14, 18, and 22⁴. The melody replacement rates for the six bars are shown in Fig 4.

Figure 4. Replacement rates of pieces A and B.

Pieces by Basic-MusicXML C and D comprised 44 bars in 3/4. The melody of the initial piece was the same as in

⁴ Bars where the initial melody was not replaced with the recommended melody] were determined by a professional composer. For example, structurally important bars such as the beginning or end of a piece have been selected.

Basic-MusicXML with 18 bars in C and D. Of those 18 bars, 12 had the same bar number in C and D. The melody replacement rates for the 12 bars are shown in Fig 5.

Figure 5. Replacement rate of pieces C and D.

In all pieces from A to D, the front of the piece had a high replacement rate. This indicates that many groups worked on the replacements in order from the front of the piece. The 22nd bar of pieces A and B is a long-toned closure note, so we expected to find few groups to replace it. However, the large number of groups that replaced it was probably due to the difference between the number of moras in the lyrics and the number of notes in Basic-MusicXML. After bar 38 of piece C and D, which is the part where the students sing the name of the school, the students were motivated to work on it and the replacement rate was high⁵.

3.2 Operation History

With the permission of the students and their parents, the experience was recorded with a small camera to preserve a history of the operation. We also recorded the screens. All recordings are time-stamped and can be time-synchronized. After reviewing some of the videos that used the Basic-MusicXML A and B, we found that in many cases, the initial melody was chosen as a result of the work, and that no replacement work was done. We will check the operation history in detail in the future.

4. DISCUSSION

The school song will be completed by combining the melody segments replaced by the students in accordance with the following.

- Developing a melody selection interface
The total number of melodies replaced by the students is 997, and even a professional composer would have difficulty combining them manually to generate a melody for the school song. We will develop a melody selection interface in which melodies that match the mora number and intonation of the lyrics for each bar are displayed at the top of the list.

⁵ The video footage of the composition experience classes shows many children singing the name of their new school.

- Developing a tool to generate musical structures
Many melodies that the students replaced did not maintain a musical structure, such as a melodic repetition structure. We plan to build a composition support tool that will generate a musical structure, which will then be used by a composer to complete the piece of the school song.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have described a user interface that recommends melodies on the basis of AI. By creating a music template called Basic-MusicXML and implementing the system in a client-server model, we enabled pupils to have a parallel experience using a web browser on a laptop owned by their school. Over the course of a one-hour composition experience class we conducted, 38.5% of the bars in which the initial melody was the same as the Basic-MusicXML melody were replaced with bars of another melody. We plan to complete the school song by combining the melody segments selected by the students.

Acknowledgments

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